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LANAS as a Metallochromic Indicator in the Complexometric Estimation of Zinc, Cadmium and Mercury

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THE reddish brown azo-dye 2-(2'-lepidylazo)-1-naphthol-4-ammonium sulphonate, LANAS (I) formed by the condensation of 1,2-naphthoquinone-4-sodium sulphonate with 2-hydrazinolepidine in presence of concentrated ammonia, is found to give sensitive colour reactions with a number of metal ions¹.

The two five membered chelate rings are formed with metal ions, involving asterisk azo nitrogen, nitrogen of quinoline ring and hydroxyl of the naphthalene ring. The colour of chelates of zinc, cadmium and mercury are discharged quickly on adding EDTA solution, so that this dye can serve as indicator in EDTA titrations.

Experimental

Dye-solution : A 0.01% (w/v) solution of LANAS in double distilled water was used as indicator in EDTA titrations.

Reagents : Standard solutions (ca $10^{-2}M$) of zinc, cadmium and mercury were prepared by dissolving analytical grade zinc oxide, cadmium or mercury metal in perchloric acid. A $10^{-2}M$ EDTA (disodium salt) solution was prepared and standardised against zinc solution with eriochrome black T as indicator. All chemicals were of analytical grade and twice distilled water was used throughout.

Recommended Procedure : To the metal solution containing 0.326 to 10.462 mg of zinc, 0.281 to 11.242 mg of cadmium and 1.0 to 200 mg of mercury, add 2 to 3 drops of 0.01% (w/v) LANAS solution and the requisite buffer (Table 1) to bring the required pH. Raise the volume to ~20 ml and titrate the contents under the given conditions with standard EDTA solution till the end point is reached.

Results and Discussion

The titrations can be performed in reverse order when dye (I) is used, cadmium(II) can be titrated between 40°-95°. All other titrations can be carried out at room temperature. In the titration of cadmium(II) addition of few drops of acetone just near the end point improves the visual change in colour at the end point. Some of the conditions necessary for the titrations are summarised in Table 1. The results of mercury(II) estimation have already been reported¹ and have been included for comparison.

In order to ensure the utility of the titration procedures, effect of various diverse ions has been studied in detail in the estimation of 1.307 mg of zinc, 2.248 mg of cadmium and 2.006 mg of mercury. The results of the studies are summarised below.

Zinc(II) estimation : The following ions did not cause interference upto the mg level mentioned in parentheses.

Fluoride, bromide, iodide(100), nitrite, nitrate, thiocyanate, sulphite, thiosulphate, tartrate, urea, ascorbic acid, borate, calcium(II) and barium(II) (80); oxalate, rhodium(III), ruthenium(III), iridium(III), platinum (II & IV), palladium(II) and copper(II)^{a,b} in equal amounts; chromate (28); phosphate (25); magnesium(II) (30); cadmium(II)^d and lanthanones(III)^c (1.5); mercury(II)^a (20); lead(II)^e (3); aluminium(III)^e (4); bismuth(III) (6) and tin(II)^e (2.8).

Cadmium(II) estimation : Fluoride, bromide (100); nitrate, nitrite, thiocyanate, sulphite, tartrate, thio-urea, hydroxylamine, borate and barium(II) (80); oxalate, calcium(II) (80); urea, phosphate (40); ascorbic acid, chromate (2); thiosulphate (12); platinum and platinum metals (1.0); copper(II)^a, lanthanides(III)^c (1.5); aluminium(III)^e (2.0); bismuth(III)^f (2.0); iron(III)^e and tin(II)^e (1.0).

In case of mercury(II) estimation the interferences are of the same order¹. Oxalate could be tolerated in large amounts. Iron, bismuth, lead and aluminium could be successfully masked. In this

a = masked with thiourea; b = with thiosulphate; c = fluoride;
 d = with iodide; e = with sulphate; f = with chloride.

NOTES

TABLE 1—TITRATIONS CONDITIONS FOR DIFFERENT METAL IONS

Metal ions	pH	Optimum concentration mg/20 ml	Buffer	Colour change	Temperature °C	Standard Deviation
Zinc(II)	3.0-4.8	0.326 to 10.462	Ac/HAc	B-Y	0 to 50	0.003
Cadmium(II)	5.8-7.5	0.381 to 11.242	hexamine/HNO ₃	B-Y	45 to 95	0.007
Mercury(II)	5.8-7.5	1.003 to 200 mg	hexamine/HNO ₃	B-YO	0 to 70	0.006

Where B=Blue, Y=Yellow, YO=Yellow Orange.

estimation chloride ion can be tolerated in large amounts in presence of silver nitrate. This fact has been made use of in masking bismuth(III) with chloride, the excess of which can be removed by adding silver nitrate.

Determination of zinc(II) in presence of cadmium(II) or mercury(II) :

Since iodide interferes seriously in case of cadmium(II) and mercury(II) estimations, the fact has been utilized in determining zinc(II) in presence of cadmium(II) or mercury(II). The procedure adopted is as follows :

To a suitable aliquot containing 1.307 mg of zinc(II) and varying amounts of cadmium or mercury or both add 1 ml 10% KI, followed by two drops of LANAS solution. Dilute the solution to 20 ml and titrate according to recommended procedure. It has been observed that Zn(II) could be titrated successfully in presence of double the amount of Cd(II) or Hg(II) when present together or above in a mixture. The percentage error was found to be ≤ 0.5 .

LANAS thus works as a good metallochromic indicator for three metal ions. Zinc(II) could be determined in presence of cadmium and mercury successfully.

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A Study on Conductance of Manganese Soaps in Isobutanol and Benzaldehyde

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TRANSITION metal soaps are well known as catalytic agents^{1,2} and also find applications in the preparation of greases³⁻⁵. In view of the importance of these soaps, it was found to be of interest to study their physical properties in different solvents. Recently the conductance behaviour of these soaps inferred that soaps form micellar aggregates in water⁶ and alcohols^{7,8}. In the present investigation, we have studied the conductance of manganese soaps (laurate, caprate and caprylate) in isobutanol and benzaldehyde at different temperatures in order to (i) determine the CMC of the soap solutions, (ii) confirm the effect of temperature if any on CMC and (iii) determine dissociation constant, K, molecular conductance at infinite dilution, λ_{∞} , activation energy of conductance, ΔE_{λ} and heat of dissociation, ΔH° .

Experimental

Isobutanol, benzaldehyde, manganese chloride, *n*-caprylic, capric and lauric acids (Merck or B.D.H. reagent grade) were used. The fatty acids were purified by distillation under reduced pressure, the purity being confirmed by b.p. measurements.

The preparation of the soaps and measurement of conductivity were described in the previous communication⁹. The reproducibility of the results was examined by repeating the measurements.

Results and Discussion

Specific conductance, k, of soap solutions (Table 1) increases with increasing concentration as

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